

ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT OF ACTIVITY OF INSURANCE COMPANIES' INVESTING PROCESS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. In this scientific thesis, increasing investment opportunities by ensuring the financial stability of insurance companies is scientifically based. In recent years, the priorities of the reform of the insurance system in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the development trends have been analyzed. Experiences of foreign countries on the development of investment activities of insurance companies are described.

Keywords: insurance, investment, financial stability, insurance premium, actuarial, life insurance, general insurance, savings.

The financial stability of insurance companies, which are an important segment of the financial market in global practice, is mainly determined by their investment activity, solvency and the amount of insurance reserves. According to the information provided by major international rating companies, there is a high correlation between the level of living conditions of the population (the amount of GDP per capita) and the share of insurance premiums in the composition of GDP, which indicates the financial stability of the insurance market of leading developed countries. In recent years, as a result of the implementation of the reforms in the development of the insurance market in our country, the share of insurance services in GDP is increasing. Increasing the financial stability of insurance companies is not only important for ensuring timely fulfillment of obligations to creditors, but also for increasing additional investment opportunities.

According to the results of 2022, a total of 41 insurance companies are operating in Uzbekistan, of which 33 belong to the general insurance sector and the remaining 8 belong to the life insurance sector. If we compare the amount of authorized capital of insurance companies by the end of 2022, it amounted to 1.884 trillion soums, this indicator increased by 18.5% compared to the corresponding period of the previous year (Table 1).

1-Table**Structure of the insurance market of Uzbekistan ¹**

№	Insurance market structure	2021 Year	2022 year	Change (+,-)
1	Number of insurance organizations <i>including on life insurance</i>	42	41	-2,4%
		8	8	0%
2	Total authorized capital of insurance organizations (billion soums)	1589,8	1884,1	+18,5%
3	Number of insurance brokers	5	7	+40%
4	Number of actuaries	5	5	0%
5	Number of insurance agents including legal entities	9581	9155	-4,4%
		2820	2625	-6,9%
6	The number of insurance organizations that are members of the Payment Guarantee Fund	23	25	+8,7%

In addition, total insurance premiums collected by insurers during 2022 increased by 67.0% and amounted to 6.23 trillion soums. During the analyzed period, life insurance payments increased by 112.6% to 1,524.68 billion. Amount to sum. In particular, payments for voluntary insurance types increased by 76.89% and amounted to 5.71 trillion soums or 91.68% (86.54% in 2021) of all insurance

¹ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Иқтисодиёт ва молия вазирлиги суғурта бозорини ривожлантириш агентлигининг расмий сайти маълумотлари асосида муаллиф томонидан тайёрланган

premiums collected by insurance organizations. During 2022, payments for compulsory insurance services increased by 3.18% and amounted to 518.04 billion sums. The main part of investment activity carried out by insurance companies corresponded to the share of deposits of commercial banks, their amount increased by 31.2% in the analyzed period and amounted to 2.896 trillion sums. We should note that in recent years, insurance companies as institutional investors have been occupying one of the top positions in the volume of trade of securities of Tashkent RFB. By the end of 2022, investments in securities by insurance companies increased by 17.5% and amounted to 1287.92 billion sums or 27.1% of the investments of insurance organizations (Table 2).

2-Table

Investment activity of insurers²

№	Indicator name	2021 Year		2022 Year		Change (+,-)
		billion	billion in soums in % of the total.	billion in soums	in soums in % of the total	
1	Total investment, including	3746,6	100	4751,7	100	+26,8%
2	Deposits	2208,5	58,9	2896,6	61	+31,2%
3	Securities	1095,9	29,3	1287,9	27,1	+17,5%
4	Loans	47,4	1,3	60,7	1,3	+28,1%
5	Real estate	247,3	6,6	358,9	7,6	+45,1%
6	Participation in the charter fund of organizations	142,2	3,8	118,2	2,5	-16,9%
7	Other investments	5,1	0,1	29,2	0,6	+471,1

² Prepared by the author based on information from the official website of the Insurance Market Development Agency of the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan

We can see it from the data on the table that the investments made as deposits in commercial banks are considered as the top investment direction made by insurance companies. Because today, among the business interest rates in the economy, I considered the interest rates offered by commercial banks on deposits to be high. Also, it can be seen that something have relatively sped up the investment activity of insurance companies in the real estate market, we should note that this indicator increased by about 50% during the analyzed period. The indicator of the participation of insurance companies in the authorized fund of organizations has a tendency to decrease, this situation can be explained by the fact that the amount of dividends received on securities of investments made by insurance companies remains at an unstable level.

Diversification of investment activities primarily provides for the stability of the insurance company's investment portfolio. It is known that the set of investment projects to which insurance companies can contribute their funds depends on the level of development of the capital market. At the moment, temporary idle funds of the can be placed in deposits of commercial banks, securities, invested in enterprises and real estate. Regulation of the composition and system of the investment portfolio is usually carried out by means of determining the minimum and maximum for the types of funds included.

In developed countries, insurance company asset placement standards, maximum and minimum quotas of insurance reserves, and a list of assets covering insurance reserves have been developed. The developed standards are regulated depending on the level of economic development, the state of financial markets, and national traditions. Investment directions of insurance companies are determined separately for the life insurance industry and for other general insurance networks. In the European Union, the United Kingdom and the United States, the responsibility for regulating the insurance market is to some extent divided between national, local and regional authorities. Each state in the United States has independent insurance

regulators. EU countries have their own regulatory bodies, but follow directives that are common to each of them.

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